

Performance of rice genotypes under semi-deepwater conditions during kharif at Sirsi

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The rice production scenario in India during the past decade presents a gloomy picture: a compound growth rate of just 1.7% in spite of a record production (93.3 million t) posted in 2001-02. These recent trends create several scenarios for the future. Land under rice is likely to decrease further and could stabilize at about 40 million ha. To meet a production target of 125 million t by 2025, all inclusive of the food requirement, seed for cultivation, storage in buffer stock, and a share for exports, productivity needs to be enhanced by 1.5 t ha⁻¹ in irrigated areas and by about 1 t ha⁻¹ in the rainfed lowlands (ICAR 2008). Rice is cultivated on more than 285,000 ha, with a production of 723,000 t (2.54 t ha⁻¹) during kharif in the Malnad area of Karnataka State; it is grown under upland, midland, and lowland conditions. In these areas, rainfall ranges from 1,300 to 3,500 mm, with an average of 2,400 mm. Farmers from this region prefer local cultivars, but the heavy rains cause long-duration varieties to lodge, leading to food-grain losses. The suitable varieties, however, are low yielders. Our study was undertaken to identify suitable genotypes for this situation under the 3-year All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project (AICRIP) in the ARS (Paddy), Sirsi.

The deepwater rice ecosystem includes areas with varying water depths (50 cm or higher) over a period of at least 10 days or more. Rice productivity in this ecosystem depends on initial crop stand and vigor, time and pattern of water accumulation, extent and duration of crop submergence (particularly in the early stages), elongation ability of the variety, and crop management practices (Srinivasa Rao et al 2009).

A field experiment was laid out at ARS Sirsi (Karnataka State) during the 2006-08 kharif seasons. Water level was maintained at more than 45 cm in experimental plots from seedling stage to physiological maturity to evaluate the top-performing genotypes among 15 test entries: IET19163 (NDR9830099, a derivative from IR31238-474-3-P1/IR41054-81-2-3-2) and IET19189 (CR2008-111, obtained from Savithri/Padmini), along with two tolerant check varieties—Sabita (NC492, IET8970), a pureline selection from Boyan released in 1986, and Purnendu (CN573-221-7-1, IET10029), a progeny of Patnai 23/Jaladhi 2, released

in 1994 (Shobha Rani et al 2008, Srinivasa Rao et al 2009), under transplanted semi-deepwater conditions. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Seedlings (20–25 d old) were transplanted at 20 × 15-cm spacing. The recommended dose of fertilizer (75:75:90 kg NPK ha⁻¹) was applied and suitable agronomic practices were observed. Observations on days to 50% flowering and the following measurements were recorded at maturity—plant height, panicle length, number of tillers per hill, grain yield, and straw yield (Shobha Rani et al 2006). The mean values for all traits were taken for ancillary traits. The data were analyzed by appropriate statistical analysis (Gomez and Gomez 1984) using the CropStat 7.2 program. The meteorological data are presented in the figure.

Flooding is a serious constraint to plant growth and survival in rainfed lowland and deepwater areas because excessive water results in partial or complete submergence of the plant. Partial submergence occurs when 40–99% of the shoot is under water. The potential of genotype under such conditions depends not only on yield but also on adaptability parameters such as seedling survival, kneeing ability, low grain shattering, and good phenotypic acceptability. As the western Ghats area of Karnataka has more than 10% of such area, the search for suitable varieties was undertaken in 2004 kharif by the Department of Genetics and Plant Breeding, ARS (Paddy), Sirsi.

Weather parameters over 3 years were uniform, except for total rainfall in July 2008 (see figure). Relative humidity and maximum/minimum temperature also showed the same trend. The results revealed a significant variation for all traits studied with respect to genotype, year, and their interaction (see table). Two genotypes showed superior performance under the AICRIP trials conducted across the country during the same period (2006–08).

Days to 50% flowering showed significant variation, ranging from 87 (2007, Sabita) to 115.5 (2006, IET19189). The mean shortest duration was recorded for Sabita (97 d), followed by IET19189 (104.8 d), IET19163 (105.3 d), and Purnendu (107.7 d). Days to 50% flowering over the years also showed significant variation: from 94.5 d in 2007 to 110.5 d in 2006. Late-maturing genotypes survived in low-lying areas of this region despite prolonged waterlogging conditions.

While plant height (cm) ranged from 88.3 cm (2006, IET19189) to 151.4 cm (2007, Purnendu), the mean tallest height was observed in Sabita (137.8 cm), followed by Purnendu (129.1 cm), IET19163 (119.5 cm), and IET19189 (114.5 cm). Variation in plant height (cm) over the years was significant and ranged from 107.9 cm (2006) to 139.5 cm (2007). Local varieties lodged and yield was compromised; the genotypes IET19163 and IET19189 were nonlodging types and might produce consistent yield.

Weather parameters recorded at AAS Unit, ARS (Paddy), Sirsi, in 2006-08.

Traits evaluated in two genotypes and two national check varieties under a heavy rainfall zone, Karnataka, India, 2006-08 kharif.

Entry	Days to 50% to flowering				Plant height (cm)				Panicle length (cm)				Tillers per hill (no.)				Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)				Straw yield (t ha ⁻¹)			
	2006	2007	2008	Mean	2006	2007	2008	Mean	2006	2007	2008	Mean	2006	2007	2008	Mean	2006	2007	2008	Mean	2006	2007	2008	Mean
IET19163	113.5*	95*	107.5*	105.3*	99	129.9*	129.5*	119.5	23.4	25.3*	24.4*	24.4	10.8*	9.1*	6.2*	8.7	7.7*	5.7*	8.5*	7.3**	7.45	7.45	9.75	8.2
IET19189	115.5*	94*	105*	104.8*	88.3	131.6*	123.5*	114.5	21.8	23.5	23.4	22.9	9.9*	1.8	5.7*	9.1*	6.5*	5.3	8.65*	6.8*	9.1	7.4	11.7*	9.4
Purnendu (national check)	107*	102*	114*	107.7*	105.5	151.4*	130.4*	129.1*	20.8	26.5*	24.7*	24.0	10.4*	7.7*	6.8*	8.3	5.4	5.35	8.9*	6.6	7.25	10.1	9.9	9.1
Sabita (national check)	106*	87	97*	96.7	138.6*	145*	129.9*	137.8*	25.6*	24.3*	23.8	24.6	10.1*	8.7*	6.2*	8.3	5.3	4.2	7.95*	5.8	7.65	7.85	11.75*	9.1
Mean	110.5**	94.5	105.9**	103.6	107.9	139.5**	128.3**	125.2	22.9	24.9	24.08		10.3**	9.3**	6.2	8.6	6.2*	5.1	8.5**	6.6	7.9	8.2	10.8**	8.95
CV (%)				0.54				10.41				9.32				9.87				13.27				22.79
		SEM ±	CD (0.05)	CD (0.01)		SEM ±	CD (0.05)	CD (0.01)		SEM ±	CD (0.05)	CD (0.01)		SEM ±	CD (0.05)	CD (0.01)		SEM ±	CD (0.05)	CD (0.01)		SEM ±	CD (0.05)	CD (0.01)
Year		0.1982	0.436	0.616		4.6085	10.143	14.313		0.7895	ns	ns		0.3008	0.662	0.934		0.3107	0.684	0.965		0.7208	1.586	2.239
Genotype		0.2289	0.504	ns		5.3215	11.713	ns		0.9116	ns	ns		0.3473	0.764	ns		0.3588	0.79	1.11		0.8323	N.S.	ns
Year × genotype		0.3965	0.873	ns		9.2171	20.287	ns		1.5789	3.475	ns		0.6015	1.324	ns		0.6214	1.368	N.S.		1.4417	3.173	ns

However, no significant variation occurred in panicle length, which ranged from 20.8 cm (2006, Purnendu) to 26.5 cm (2007, Purnendu). The mean longest panicle length was observed in Sabita (24.57 cm), followed by IET19163 (24.37 cm), Purnendu (24.0 cm), and IET19189 (22.9 cm). There was a nonsignificant variation in panicle length over the years (range, 22.9 cm [2006] to 24.9 cm [2007]). Tillers per hill showed significant variation and ranged from 5.7 (2008, IET19189) to 11.8 (2007, IET19189); the highest mean number of tillers per hill was observed in IET19189 (9.13), followed by IET19163 (8.7), Sabita (8.33), and Purnendu (8.3). Tillers per hill over the years also showed significant variation and ranged from 6.23 in 2008 to 10.3 in 2006.

Grain yield ranged from 4.2 t ha⁻¹ (2007, Sabita) to 8.9 t ha⁻¹ (2008, Purnendu), with the highest mean grain yield coming from IET19163 (7.3 t ha⁻¹), followed by IET19189 (6.8 t ha⁻¹), Purnendu (6.6 t ha⁻¹), and Sabita (5.8 t ha⁻¹). Variation in grain yield over the years was significant and ranged from 5.1 t ha⁻¹ (2007) to 8.5 t ha⁻¹ (2008). Straw yield ranged from 7.3 t ha⁻¹ (2006, Purnendu) to 11.8 t ha⁻¹ (2008, Sabita). The highest mean straw yield was observed in IET19189 (9.4 t ha⁻¹), followed by Sabita and Purnendu (9.1 t ha⁻¹) and IET19163 (8.2 t ha⁻¹). There was significant variation in straw yield over the years and it ranged from 7.9 t ha⁻¹ (2006) to 10.8 t ha⁻¹ (2008).

The genotypes IET19163 (long bold grains, 105 d to 50% flowering, 7.3 t grain ha⁻¹, 8.22 t straw ha⁻¹) and IET19189 (long bold grains, 105 d to 50% flowering, 6.8 t grain ha⁻¹, 9.4 t straw ha⁻¹) showed statistical superiority over the two checks. These would be good alternatives for planting in the intermittently flooded and low-lying areas of Karnataka.

References

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